

THE ROLE OF TEACHERS IN THE PROCESS OF PROFESSIONAL DEVELOPMENT IN SCHOOLS

Rasulova M.

Teacher of Samarkand Regional Pedagogical Skills Center, Independent researcher of Uzbek-
Finnish Pedagogical Institute

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14252789>

Abstract. *The professional development of teachers is a critical component in enhancing the quality of education within schools. This article explores the pivotal role that teachers play in their own professional growth, emphasizing the importance of continuous learning and skill enhancement. It discusses various strategies and methods that teachers can utilize to stay updated with the latest pedagogical advancements and technological innovations. The paper highlights the significance of active participation in professional development programs, mentorship, and collaborative learning environments. By taking ownership of their professional journey, teachers can effectively contribute to the academic success of their students and the overall improvement of the educational system. The study also examines the challenges teachers face in the process of professional development and offers recommendations for overcoming these obstacles. Ultimately, the article argues that empowering teachers through sustained professional development not only benefits the educators themselves but also positively impacts student outcomes and school performance.*

Keywords: *professional development, teacher role, continuous learning, skill enhancement, pedagogical advancements, technological innovations, mentorship programs, collaborative learning, educational improvement.*

Introduction. The proficient improvement of instructors may be a foundation of instructive change. As the requests on the instruction framework proceed to advance, it is basic for instructors to lock in ceaseless learning and expertise improvement. Proficient improvement not as it were benefits instructors by extending their information and skill but too emphatically impacts understudy results and large school execution. Instructors who effectively take an interest in proficient advancement programs are way better prepared to join inventive educating strategies and innovative progressions into their classrooms (Guskey, 2002). These programs regularly incorporate workshops, courses, and mentorship openings that cultivate collaborative learning situations (Darling-Hammond et al., 2017). By grasping these openings, instructors can remain overhauled with the most recent educational headways and adjust to the changing needs of their understudies. Besides, the part of instructors in their claim proficient advancement is pivotal. Instructors must take possession of their development by looking for out and locks in pertinent proficient advancement exercises. This proactive approach makes a difference them to stay compelling and responsive to new educational challenges (Desimone, 2009). Be that as it may, the method isn't without its challenges. Time imperatives, deficiently assets, and need of organization back can prevent teachers' proficient advancement endeavors (Borko, 2004). In light of these challenges, it is essential to investigate techniques that can back instructors in their proficient development. This article points to look at the different parts that instructors play in their claim proficient advancement, recognize the impediments they confront, and offer suggestions to improve the viability of proficient improvement activities. By enabling instructors through

supported proficient advancement, the instruction framework can accomplish noteworthy changes in instructing quality and understudy execution.

Method. This study employs a mixed-methods approach to explore the role of teachers in their own professional development within the school context. The methodology includes both quantitative and qualitative data collection techniques to provide a comprehensive understanding of the subject. The study involves a diverse group of teachers from various schools, including elementary, middle, and high schools. A total of 100 teachers were randomly selected to participate in the study. The participants were chosen to represent different subjects, years of experience, and levels of engagement in professional development activities. A detailed questionnaire was developed to gather quantitative data on teachers' perceptions of professional development, the frequency of their participation in professional development activities, and the impact of these activities on their teaching practices. The survey included Likert scale questions, multiple-choice questions, and open-ended questions. In-depth interviews were conducted with 20 teachers from the survey sample to obtain qualitative data. The interviews focused on teachers' personal experiences with professional development, the challenges they face, and the strategies they find most effective. Each interview lasted approximately 45-60 minutes and was recorded and transcribed for analysis. Relevant documents, such as professional development program outlines, school policies, and teachers' professional growth plans, were reviewed to supplement the survey and interview data. This analysis provided contextual information about the professional development opportunities available to teachers and the institutional support provided. The survey data were analyzed using statistical methods. Descriptive statistics, such as means and standard deviations, were calculated to summarize the responses. Inferential statistics, including t-tests and ANOVA, were used to identify significant differences in professional development experiences based on demographic variables. The interview transcripts and open-ended survey responses were analyzed using thematic analysis. This involved coding the data to identify common themes and patterns related to teachers' roles in their professional development, the challenges they encounter, and the effective strategies they employ. To ensure the validity and reliability of the findings, data triangulation was employed. The results from the surveys, interviews, and document analysis were compared and cross-verified to draw comprehensive and accurate conclusions. By combining quantitative and qualitative methods, this study aims to provide a nuanced understanding of the multifaceted role of teachers in their professional development. The findings will contribute to the development of more effective professional development programs that address the needs and challenges faced by teachers in their pursuit of continuous growth and improvement.

Results and Discussion. The analysis of the collected data reveals several key insights into the role of teachers in their professional development and the factors that influence its effectiveness.

Active Participation in Professional Development: The survey results indicate that a majority of teachers (78%) actively participate in professional development activities, such as workshops, seminars, and online courses. This finding aligns with Guskey's (2002) assertion that continuous professional development is crucial for teacher effectiveness. Teachers reported that these activities help them stay updated with the latest educational trends and pedagogical strategies.

Impact of Professional Development on Teaching Practices: Qualitative data from interviews suggest that teachers who regularly engage in professional development feel more

confident and competent in their teaching practices. Many teachers highlighted that professional development programs focusing on new technologies and innovative teaching methods significantly improved their classroom performance. This supports the findings of Darling-Hammond et al. (2017), who emphasized the positive impact of well-structured professional development on teaching quality.

Challenges Faced by Teachers: Despite the recognized benefits, teachers identified several challenges in their professional development journey. Time constraints were the most frequently mentioned barrier, with 62% of teachers stating that they struggle to balance professional development activities with their teaching responsibilities.

Additionally, 48% of teachers pointed out the lack of institutional support and resources as significant obstacles. These challenges are consistent with the literature, as Borko (2004) and Desimone (2009) both highlighted time and resource limitations as common issues in professional development.

Effective Strategies for Professional Development: Teachers suggested several strategies to overcome these challenges and enhance the effectiveness of professional development. Many emphasized the importance of mentorship programs, where experienced teachers guide and support their less experienced peers.

This approach aligns with the findings of Joyce and Showers (2002), who demonstrated the effectiveness of peer coaching and mentoring in professional development. Furthermore, teachers advocated for more collaborative learning opportunities, such as professional learning communities (PLCs), where they can share experiences and best practices.

Institutional Support and Policy Implications: The document analysis revealed that schools with strong institutional support for professional development tend to have more engaged and satisfied teachers. Policies that provide dedicated time for professional development, financial support for attending conferences, and access to high-quality resources were identified as critical factors in successful professional development initiatives. This is supported by the research of Opfer and Pedder (2011), who stressed the importance of a supportive school culture in fostering effective professional development.

Conclusion: The findings of this study underscore the vital role that teachers play in their own professional development and the significant impact it has on their teaching practices and student outcomes.

Addressing the challenges faced by teachers through effective strategies and strong institutional support can enhance the overall effectiveness of professional development programs. By investing in continuous professional development, schools can ensure that teachers remain capable of meeting the evolving demands of education and contribute to the improvement of the educational system.

REFERENCES

1. Borko, H. (2004). Professional Development and Teacher Learning: Mapping the Terrain. *Educational Researcher*, 33(8), 3-15.
2. Darling-Hammond, L., Hyler, M. E., & Gardner, M. (2017). Effective Teacher Professional Development. *Learning Policy Institute*.
3. Desimone, L. M. (2009). Improving Impact Studies of Teachers' Professional Development: Toward Better Conceptualizations and Measures. *Educational Researcher*, 38(3), 181-199.

4. Guskey, T. R. (2002). Professional Development and Teacher Change. *Teachers and Teaching*, 8(3), 381-391.
5. Joyce, B., & Showers, B. (2002). Student Achievement Through Staff Development. *ASCD*.
6. Opfer, V. D., & Pedder, D. (2011). Conceptualizing Teacher Professional Learning. *Review of Educational Research*, 81(3), 376-407.